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Development and validation of an Indian music therapy intervention for kapha-related disorders: integrating time theory and circadian dosha cycles through a Raga Module (RM)

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Abstract- In Ayurvedic philosophy, *Kapha* in its balanced state produces *Ojas*-a vital essence linked to emotional resilience, reproductive health, and immune strength. Disruption of *Kapha* may result in *Ojas Kshaya*, marked by emotional states such as sadness and disgust, and associated with clinical conditions including PCOS, diabetes, obesity, and breast cancer. While classical texts like the *Charaka Samhita* recognize music's therapeutic potential, there is no validated Raga Module (RM) designed to address *Kapha*-related emotional disturbances in alignment with Ayurvedic time theory and the circadian rhythm of Doshas. This study aimed (1) To design a clinically relevant RM targeting psychological effects of *Kapha* imbalance, and (2) To validate its content through expert evaluation. *Ragas* featuring *ri*, and *dha Teevra Svaras*, evoking *Shringara rasa* (love and joy) were selected from classical and contemporary sources. A panel of 15 experts from music and Ayurveda assessed the selections using a Likert scale. Content Validity Ratio (CVR) was calculated to refine the module. The final RM comprises 28 *Ragas*: 11 from Kalyan, 7 from Bilawal, and 10 from *Khamaj Thaats*, achieving an average CVR of 0.60, surpassing Lawshe's threshold of 0.49, indicating strong expert consensus. Modal parallels between Indian *Ragas* and Western jazz structures, particularly *Ragas* with *Teevra ri* and *dha*, which align tonally with D# and A# in modes like E and B Lydian, B Ionian, and F# Mixolydian, offer a compelling basis for cross-cultural emotional expression. The validated RM presents a promising framework for addressing *Kapha*-related emotional imbalances.

Keywords: Music Therapy, *Kapha Dosha*, *Ojas*, *Raga Module*

INTRODUCTION

In *Ayurveda*, health is defined as a state of equilibrium in which the three *Doshas*-*Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha*-function harmoniously; the digestive fire operates optimally; body tissues and waste elimination are balanced; and the mind, senses, and spirit are content and clear.¹ Classical *Ayurvedic* texts emphasize that disease arises from disturbances in both physiological *Doshas* (*Vata*, *Pitta*, *Kapha*) and *Gunas* or psychological qualities (*Rajas* and *Tamas*), underscoring

the interconnectedness of body and mind.² *Vata*, composed of air and space, governs movement, circulation, and neural activity; its imbalance is associated with anxiety and neurological dysfunction.³ *Pitta*, composed of fire and water, regulates digestion, metabolism, and cognitive processing; when disturbed, it may lead to inflammation and emotional irritability.⁴ *Kapha*, composed of water and earth, provides structural integrity, lubrication, and emotional steadiness; its excess is linked to lethargy and heaviness.⁵ *Dosha-Guna* imbalances reciprocally disrupt mind-body equilibrium, requiring integrated treatment.⁶

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In *Ayurvedic* physiology, balanced *Vata* manifests as *Prana* (parasympathetic tone)⁷ *Pitta* as *Tejas* (mitochondrial efficiency)⁸ and *Kapha* as *Ojas* (immunological resilience)⁹.

Ojas is nourished through balanced tissue metabolism, a process supported by *Kapha*'s anabolic and stabilizing properties.¹⁰ Balanced *Kapha* further facilitates the production and preservation of *Ojas*, which nurtures reproductive fluids and enhances fertility.^{11,12} An imbalance in *Kapha* can result in metabolic disorders like obesity and insulin resistance, thereby elevating the risk of diabetes.¹³ A deficiency in *Ojas* results in fear, weakness, mental instability, and sensory impairments.¹⁴ and is a key factor in the pathogenesis of *Rajayakshma*, a wasting disease associated with *Dhatu Kshaya* and immunodeficiency.¹⁵ To rejuvenate *Ojas*, the vital essence of strength and immunity, *Charaka* advocates rejuvenating therapies that nourish both body and mind. This includes savouring wholesome foods, absorbing emotionally uplifting experiences, and immersing oneself in the healing resonance of instrumental and vocal music.¹⁶

Indian music is structured around seven fundamental technical elements: *Nada* (primordial vibration), *Shruti* (microtonal pitch), *Svara* (musical note), *Raga* (melodic framework), *Tala* (rhythm cycle), *Rasa* (aesthetic essence), and *Thaat* (parent scale). The seven primary notes- *sa, ri, ga, ma, pa, dha, ni* - are referred to as the *Shuddha Svaras* or pure notes of the Indian musical scale. Each of these *Svaras*, except for *Shadja* (*sa*) and *Panchama* (*pa*), can be altered in pitch. These altered forms are called *Komal* (flattened) when lowered and *Teevra* (sharpened) when raised. Since *sa* and *pa* remain constant and unmodified, they are considered stable or fixed pitches. In contrast, *Rishabha* (*ri*), *Gandhara* (*ga*), *Madhyama* (*ma*), *Dhaivata* (*dha*), and *Nishada* (*ni*) exist in two variants, giving rise to a total of twelve distinct notes in Indian classical music.¹⁷ Effective application of music therapy is rooted in precise intonation and the careful use of these seven technical aspects. At its core, Indian music strives to awaken *Rasa*, the deep emotional essence whose realization promotes inner joy and psychological balance, thereby facilitating emotional healing.¹⁸

Balancing Dosh through Music

A sound adorned with melodic tones and shaped by the movement of tonal patterns, which evokes delight in the hearts and minds of listeners, is known as a *Raga*. *Raga* can be broadly classified according to the number

of *Svaras* employed in its ascending (*Arohana*) and descending (*Avarohana*) movements: *Audava*-comprising five notes (pentatonic); *Shadava*-comprising six notes (hexatonic); and *Sampurna*-comprising seven notes (heptatonic).¹⁹ *Bhatkhande* developed the “*Thaat*” system to organize Hindustani *ragas*. A *Thaat* is a set of seven selected notes (*Svaras*) used to group *ragas* with similar melodic structures and the potential to evoke specific *Rasa*, or aesthetic mood. *Rasa*, considered a subtle bioenergetic principle, serves as an integrative link between the physical and psychological realms, exerting influence over cognition and emotional states. Among the nine classical *Rasas*, four- *Shringara* (Love), *Shanta* (Tranquility), *Veera* (Self-Assurance), and *Karuna* (Compassion)-are particularly significant in therapeutic contexts. These *Rasas* can be evoked through specific *Svara* combinations within *Ragas*: *Teevra ri* and *Teevra dha* elicit *Shringara Rasa*; *Komal ri* and *Komal dha* cultivate *Shanta and Karuna Rasa*; while *Komal ga* and *Komal ni* induce *Veera Rasa*.²⁰

In accordance with the *Samanya-Visheca Siddhanta* (*SVS*)-the *Ayurvedic* principle stating that opposites diminish imbalances-music expressing *Veera Rasa* may help mitigate *Vata Dosha*, typically marked by fear and anxiety; *Shanta* and *Karuna Rasas* may temper *Pitta Dosha*, associated with anger; and *Shringara Rasa* may counterbalance the inertia and melancholy linked to *Kapha Dosha*. As described in classical *Ayurvedic* texts, Indian classical music is structured to promote *Dosha* equilibrium.²¹ Moreover, music serves as a powerful tool to guide the mind toward *Sattva Guna* (goodness) by encouraging mindful absorption to musical notes, thereby reducing *Rajas* and *Tamas*-qualities associated with disease manifestation.²²

Studies have shown that music therapy can benefit various metabolic disorders, including PCOS²³, postpartum depression²⁴, and breast cancer²⁵. Music therapy produced a medium-to-large effect size in reducing psychological stress, with particularly strong improvements in anxiety, sadness, and emotional distress.²⁶ Additionally, music therapy can reduce healthcare costs while improving patient outcomes, particularly in publicly funded and insurance-supported settings.²⁷

Ancient texts such as *Sangeeta Makaranda* recommend listening to *Ragas* based on time theory.²⁸ Correlating it to the circadian cycle of *Doshas* as per *Ayurveda* may help in bringing balance in both physiological and psychological levels. *Bhatkhande* classified *Ragas*

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according to their prescribed times of performance, highlighting the therapeutic value of synchronizing music with natural rhythms. He based these timings on *Praharas*, which are three-hour divisions aligned with the progression of the sun. This temporal framework parallels the body's diurnal biorhythmic shifts, as described in *Ayurveda* through the alternating predominance of *Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha* (see Figure 1).²⁹ However, there are no structured *Raga* module (RM) available that are based on time theory for balancing *Kapha*, which can also be used for healing certain women-related issues.

METHODOLOGY

The study methodology encompasses two stages:-

1. Design and development of the *Raga* Module (RM) to address the psychological effects of *Kapha* imbalance,

specifically sadness and disgust, by inducing *Shringara Rasa*

2. Content validation of the RM as per the standard guidelines.³⁰

Design and development of Raga module (RM) for Kapha imbalance

To begin with, a thorough review of the Ancient and Contemporary music texts carried out [Table 1] Four volumes of Contemporary music texts were included for the review.^{20,31-34} We identified 11 *Ragas* from *Kalyan Thaata*, 7 *Ragas* from *Bilawal Thaata*, and 10 *Ragas* from *Khamaj Thaata* that were associated with the evocation of *Shringara Rasa*, along with the specific *Svaras* employed in each. A total of 28 *Ragas*, selected based on the presence of *ri*, and *dha*, *Teevra Svaras*, were compiled and subsequently forwarded to experts for validation [Table 2]

Table 1- Ragas for Alleviating Psychological Manifestations of Kapha Imbalance-Targeting Sadness and Disgust through the Induction of Shringara Rasa

Thaat	Raga	Notation	Reference	
Kalyan Thaata	Hindol	Jati of this Raga is Shadava – Sampoorna. Svaras used are Teevra ri, both Komal and Teevra ga, both Komal and Teevra ma, Teevra dha, and both Komal and Teevra ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 2. p.132.	
	Goud Sarang	Jati of this Raga is Sampoorna – Sampoorna. Svaras used are Teevra ri, Teevra ga, both Shuddha and Teevra ma, Teevra dha, and Teevra ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 2. p. 91.	
	Sanjh	Jati of the Raga is Auduva – Auduva. Svaras used are all Teevra Svaras only.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 62.	
	Raja Kalyan	Jati of the Raga is Auduva- Shadava. Svaras used are Teevra ri, Shuddha ga, Teevra ma, Teevra dha and Teevra ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 6	
	Shuddha Kalyan	Jati of this Raga is Auduva – Sampoorna. Svaras used are all Teevra Svaras only.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 115.	
	Shyam kedar	Jati of this Raga is Shadava – Shadava. Svaras used are Teevra ri, Komal and Teevra ma, Teevra dh, and both Komal and Teevra ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 130.	
	Yaman Kalyan	Jati of this Raga is Sampoorna – Sampoorna. Svaras used are all Teevra Svaras only.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 218.	
	Shree Kalyan	Jati of the Raga is Auduva – Auduva. Svaras used are all Teevra svaras only.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 101.	
	Viranchimukha	Jati of the Raga is Auduva- Shadava. Svaras used are Teevra ri, Teevra ga, both Shuddha and Teevra ma, Teevra dha, and Teevra ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 213.	
	Vyjayanti	Jati of the Raga is Auduva – Auduva. Svaras used are all Teevra Svaras only.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 215.	
	Adbut kalyan	Jati of the Raga is Auduva – Auduva. Svaras used are all Teevra Svaras only.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 224.	
	Bilawal Thaata	Shuddha Malhar	Jati of the Raga is Auduva – Auduva. Svaras used are Teevra ri, Shuddha ma and Teevra dha.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 117.
		Shankara	Jati of the Raga is Auduva- Shadava. Svaras used are Teevra ri, Teevra ga, Teevra dha and Teevra ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 81.
Yamini Bilawal		Jati of this Raga is Sampoorna – Sampoorna. Svaras used are all Teevra Svaras excepting ma of which both Shuddha and Teevra Svaras are used.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 219.	
Shukla Bilawal		Jati of this Raga is Shadava – Sampoorna. Svaras used are Teevra ri, Teevra ga, Shuddha ma, Teevra dha, and both Komal and Teevra ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 127.	
Nata Kambhoj		Jati of this Raga is Shadava – Sampoorna. . Svaras used are Teevra ri, Teevra ga, Shuddha ma, Teevra dha, and both Komal and Teevra ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 283.	

continued...

	Alaiya Bahar	Jati of this Raga is Shadava – Sampoorna. Svaras used are Teevra ri, both Komal and Teevra ga, Shuddha ma, Teevra dha, and both Komal and Teevra ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 227.
Khamaj Thaat	Desh	Jati of this Raga is Auduva – Sampoorna. Svaras used are Teevra ri, Teevra ga, Shuddha ma, Teevra dha, and both Komal and Teevra ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 2. p. 6.
	Maghava	Jati of this Raga is Auduva – Sampoorna. Svaras used are Teevra ri, Teevra ga, Shuddha ma, Teevra dha and Komal ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 280.
	Rageshree	Jati of this Raga is Auduva- Shadava. Svaras used are Teevra ri, Teevra ga, Komal ma, Teevra dha and both Komal and Teevra ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 3.
	Ravichandrika	Jati of this Raga is Sampoorna – Shadava. Svaras used are Teevra ri, Teevra ga, Shuddha ma, Teevra dha, and both Komal and Teevra ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p.32
	Sajan	Jati of this Raga is Auduva – Sampoorna. Svaras used are Teevra ri, Teevra ga, Shuddha ma, Teevra dha, and both Komal and Teevra ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p.48
	Sorat	There are two types of Sorat Raga- Auduva - Shadava and Auduva-Auduva. Svaras used in both types are Teevra ri, Shuddha ma, Teevra dha, and both Komal and Teevra ni	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 151.
	Khambavati Kamaj	Jati of this Raga is Auduva – Sampoorna. Svaras used are Teevra ri, Teevra ga, Shuddha ma, Teevra dha, and both Komal and Teevra ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 275.
	Koushiya	Jati of this Raga is Shadava – Sampoorna. Svaras used are Teevra ri, Teevra ga, Shuddha Ma, Teevra dha and Komal ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 276.
	Sanjivini	Svaras used are Teevra ri, Teevra ga, Shuddha ma, Teevra dha, and Komal ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 291.
	Tilak Kamod	Jati of this Raga is Shadava – Sampoorna. Svaras used are Teevra ri, Teevra ga, Shuddha ma, Teevra dha and Teevra ni.	Raganidhi: A comparative study of Hindustani and Karnatak Ragas. Vol 4. p. 180

Experts for validation

A structured validation process was employed to obtain expert feedback on the proposed RM. Experts were invited based on the following eligibility criteria: (a) a minimum of five years of clinical experience in *Ayurvedic* practice; (b) active engagement in treating medical conditions using music as an adjunct therapy, with formal training in Indian Classical Music; (c) musicians possessing sufficient *Ayurvedic* knowledge certified by the Health Sector Skill Council’s competency enhancement course in music therapy; and (d) affiliation with music institutions, having undergone training under esteemed *Vidwans* (masters in music). A total of twenty-five experts were approached. Of these, eighteen responded and were screened against the eligibility criteria. Fifteen experts comprising clinicians, academicians, and two musicians qualified and consented to participate. All fifteen eligible experts provided evaluative feedback on the RM. The details are mentioned in [Table 2]

Table 2- Details of the experts for validation of the

Qualification	No RM experts	Experience in years (mean ± SD)
MD	4	12.33 ± 6.12
M.A	1	12.5 ± 6.45
Ph. D	2	7.0 ± 1.41
M.Phil	1	5.0 ± 0
BAMS	6	25.0 ± 0
Postgraduate	1	13.0 ± 0
Total	15	12.06 ± 6.24

Methodology for validation

A structured Google Form was developed to facilitate expert evaluation, incorporating detailed information on each *Raga* including its recommended time of rendition or listening, the *Rasa* evoked, *Svaras* employed, and therapeutic applicability. Respondents were asked to rate each item based on the stated objectives using a five-point Likert scale (not at all, a little, moderate, very much, extremely), with additional space provided for subjective feedback. For the purpose of content validation, *Ragas* receiving ratings of “very much” and “extremely” were classified as therapeutically beneficial.

Statistical analysis

The data was organized in Microsoft Excel version 2019. The Content Validity Ratio (CVR) for each *Raga* was calculated using Lawshe’s formula: $CVR = (NE-N/2) / (N/2)$, where *NE* represents the number of experts rating the item as ‘essential’, and *N* is the total number of experts consulted.

Content Validity Ratio

The finalized RM encompassed 28 *Ragas*, distributed across three *Thaats*: 11 from *Kalyan*, 7 from *Bilawal*, and 10 from *Khamaj*. The module achieved an average Content Validity Ratio (CVR) of 0.49, reflecting strong overall content validity and expert consensus. The details of Expert Evaluation of *Ragas*: Time Designations, *Thaat* Classification, and CVR Scores are depicted in Table 3.

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Table 3- *Ragas, Thaats* Classifications, Designated Time Frames, Validation Scores, and Content Validity Ratios (CVRs)

Ragas	Thaat	Time	Experts Rated ≥ 3	Total Experts	CVR
Hindol	Kalyan	3AM-6AM	13	15	0.73
Goud Saranga	Kalyan	12PM-3PM	13	15	0.73
Sanj	Kalyan	3AM-6AM	13	15	0.73
Raja Kalyan	Kalyan	9PM-12AM	14	15	0.86
Shuddha Kalyan	Kalyan	6PM-9PM	14	15	0.86
Shyam Kedar	Kalyan	9PM-12AM	13	15	0.73
Yaman Kalyan	Kalyan	6PM-9PM	14	15	0.86
Shree Kalyan	Kalyan	9PM-12AM	14	15	0.86
Viranchimukha	Kalyan	9PM-12AM	12	15	0.6
Vyjayanti	Kalyan	9PM-12AM	13	15	0.73
Adbut Kalyan	Kalyan	6PM-9PM	13	15	0.73
Shuddha Malhar	Bilawal	9PM-12AM	14	15	0.86
Kukubh Bilawal	Bilawal	6AM-9AM	13	15	0.73
Shankara	Bilawal	9PM-12AM	12	15	0.6
Yamini Bilawal	Bilawal	9PM-12AM	13	15	0.73
Shukla Bilawal	Bilawal	6AM-9AM	13	15	0.73
Nata Kambhoji	Bilawal	9AM-12PM	12	15	0.6
Alaiya Bahar	Bilawal	6AM-9AM	12	15	0.6
Desh	Khamaj	9PM-12AM	15	15	1
Tilak Kamod	Khamaj	6PM-9PM	14	15	0.86
Meghava	Khamaj	9PM-12AM	13	15	0.73
Rageshree	Khamaj	9PM-12AM	14	15	0.86
Ravichandrika	Khamaj	9PM-12AM	14	15	0.86
Sajan	Khamaj	9PM-12AM	13	15	0.73
Sorat	Khamaj	6AM-9AM	13	15	0.73
Khambavati	Khamaj	9PM-12AM	13	15	0.73
Koushiya	Khamaj	9PM-12AM	13	15	0.73
Sanjivini	Khamaj	9PM-12AM	14	15	0.86

Fig.1- Diurnal circadian cycle of *Vata, Pitta, Kapha* and the appropriate *Raga* based on the time theory of *Ragas* ³¹⁻³⁴

DISCUSSION

This study presents the development and validation of a RM specifically designed to address diseases associated with *Kapha* imbalance, including menstrual disorders, breast cancer, digestive dysfunction, obesity, fungal infections, asthma, nephrolithiasis, and lymphadenopathy.³⁵ To the best of our knowledge, this represents the first validated RM targeting *Kapha*-related pathologies. The module was developed following an extensive review of both scientific literature and classical *Ayurvedic* texts, with the specific aim of addressing the emotional imbalances commonly associated with *Kapha*-related disorders-particularly psychological stress, sadness, disgust, and depression, which are frequently experienced. The framework was validated by a panel of interdisciplinary experts, representing a unique synthesis of *Ayurvedic*, musical, and clinical expertise. This comprised two scholars with doctoral degrees in music; four *Ayurvedic* physicians with MD qualifications who actively integrate music therapy into their clinical practice; and six *Ayurvedic* doctors holding BAMS degrees, all of whom are also practicing music therapists. Additionally, the panel included accomplished musicians with postgraduate qualifications in music specifically, one with an MA, one with an MPhil, and one with a postgraduate degree with music as the major subject. Furthermore, each component of the module was individually validated for its emotional and physiological efficacy, ensuring its suitability for addressing the therapeutic needs and constraints associated with *Kapha* imbalance. The RM offers notable adaptability and cost-effectiveness, enabling individuals to engage with the intervention in accessible settings for instance, by listening through headphones during short breaks at the workplace. Significantly, early application of the module in individuals exhibiting *Kapha*-genic symptoms may aid in delaying the progression of disease and reducing the severity of related comorbid conditions.

Notably, the Western modal equivalents of *Kalyan*, *Bilawal*, and *Khamaj Thaats* are the Lydian, Ionian, and Mixolydian modes, respectively.³⁶ The *Ionian*, *Lydian*, and *Mixolydian* modes are foundational to Jazz and Blues improvisation. These modes are not only structurally significant but also emotionally expressive, shaping the melodic and harmonic language of jazz.³⁷ Interestingly, *Ragas* that feature *Teevra ri* and *dha*, known to evoke feelings of love and joy, exhibit tonal similarities with the

sharp degrees D# and A# found in Western modes such as E and B *Lydian*³⁸, B *Ionian*³⁹, and F# *Mixolydian*³⁸. In an experiment investigating the emotional connotations of diatonic modes, nonmusician participants listened to pairs of melodies and identified which sounded happier. The Ionian mode was consistently rated as the happiest, likely due to its strong familiarity in Western music. Although Mixolydian was expected to be perceived as happier than Lydian, nearly half of the participants rated Lydian as the more emotionally positive mode.⁴⁰ This shared harmonic vocabulary enriches the therapeutic promise of both traditions, inviting deeper exploration into their expressive and integrative capacities.

CONCLUSION

The modal correspondence between Indian *Ragas* and Western Jazz structures offers a compelling framework for cross-cultural emotional expression. *Ragas* incorporating *Teevra ri* and *dha*, tones traditionally associated with love and joy, demonstrate tonal affinities with sharpened scale degrees (D# and A#) present in Western modes such as E and B *Lydian*, B *Ionian*, and F# *Mixolydian*. These parallels support a shared emotional vocabulary across musical traditions. This study introduces a validated RM comprising Twenty eight *Ragas* specifically selected to address *Kapha* imbalance, which can also be used for healing certain women related issues. The RM is a flexible and cost-effective intervention that can be accessed in everyday settings such as via headphones during work breaks and, when applied early in individuals with *Kapha*-genic symptoms, may help delay disease progression and reduce associated comorbidities.

To establish clinical utility, further investigations are required to evaluate both feasibility and therapeutic efficacy. In pursuit of this, a randomized clinical trial has been registered with the Clinical Trials Registry of India. Upon successful testing, the RM holds promise as an adjunctive intervention within diverse clinical settings, enhancing integrative and culturally attuned therapeutic approaches.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interest.

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